

Developer Portal: improving software collaboration

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

A “developer portal” centralises information, improves collaboration, and enhances productivity by providing a centralized hub for resources and tools. It enforces consistency, transparency, and scalability, making it easier to manage projects and maintain security. Ultimately, it fosters innovation and community among teams involved in software development or data science. Developer portals achieve this through:

- Centralising Resources: All the necessary tools, documents, and information are made available in a single place.
- Templates and Best Practices: It provides templates and guidelines to help developers start new projects quickly and correctly, whilst integrating them with other tools from the outset.
- Integration with Tools: It connects with other tools and services that developers use, making their workflow smoother.

This activity has focused on utilising “Backstage”, a framework for creating Developer Portals, to create a demonstration Developer Portal for the CEDA Development Team. The resulting code has been developed in a way such that it should be relatively easy to install in other EDS Data Centres.

Rationale for the work

A common analogy given for a developer portal is that of a “kitchen for a chef”. Kitchens generally contain within them the tools needed to create and serve dishes, to the extent that finding an oven outside of a kitchen is an oddity. Just as food can be prepared anywhere, software engineering can be performed in many places; it is however much easier to create high quality food in a fully stocked kitchen, similarly it is easier to create high quality software in a developer portal.

The CEDA development team has a wide range of responsibilities, from managing community libraries for data access (such as DataPoint), to maintaining the CEDA Archive interfaces and catalogues (MOLES), to the international ESGF collaboration for CMIP. CEDA engineers are also

responsible for user facing services on the JASMIN supercomputer. CEDA has tens of thousands of users, hundreds of services and the equivalent of thousands of computers to monitor.

Other EDS data centres share many of the same issues and difficulties as CEDA, and there is very likely a high degree of commonality in possible solutions to these problems

Methodology

In common with many agencies developing software solutions, there are several categories of people in CEDA who create and/or use the software we produce. For example:

- Software engineers are primarily interested in the creation of new software. They tend to be less concerned with documenting or monitoring software once deployed.
- DevOps engineers are primarily concerned with the operation, monitoring and reliability of new software. They are less concerned with the coding standards within this software.
- Data engineers are primarily concerned with speed and simplicity of development. They are less concerned with code quality and documentation.

In other words, different groups have different priorities when creating software. These priorities (and the de-prioritisation of other aspects of good quality software development) cause different issues for other teams.

An example of this might be an application developer who produces high-quality code but does not update the documentation after a change. The deployment team may be entirely dependent on this documentation to redeploy after a failure and so are unable to help once the documentation is out of date. Similarly whilst an application developer may work on only a couple of codebases at a time, a data engineer may have hundreds of small pieces of software partially deployed across many servers or data pipelines. This can make it almost impossible for other team members to find software that may need updating after a security incident.

To find solutions to these common problems, some CEDA staff were involved in trialling this Developer Portal and seeing how it could address these issues.

One functionality provided by the prototype is the ability to construct software templates, whereby a user can input a minimum set of data and this will create a fully documented, quality-assured software package that only needs tests and business-specific variables to be added. The benefit of this is that all quality measures are automatically configured.

Lessons learnt

The prototyping of a Developer Portal has highlighted significant differences in individuals' approaches to quality code within the CEDA team.

What works for some doesn't always work for others

A template for a "public Python library" was created, and broadly welcomed by software developers within CEDA as a mechanism to eliminate the "boring" parts of coding and allow work purely on the new and interesting features, it was felt that this template provided an easier and simpler development process overall by automating quality tools. This exact same template was greeted much less favourably by data scientists who felt it added significant complexity and an unreasonable level of burden to their work. Many of the tools the template introduced, such as McCabe's cyclomatic complexity analysis which measures the complexity of a program (well known to most software engineers) were largely unknown to the data scientists who were not used to the more formal coding style it recommended.

A Developer portal offers different advantages to teams who have varying quality requirements.

For example, software engineers are typically more concerned with making sure their services are up-to-date and are utilising current dependencies. However, the changing versioning standards in most ecosystems make this more complicated for developers of libraries and installable components. The templating system of the Developer Portal removes the complexity of managing different dependency management paradigms, making interdependent software components easier to manage.

A key benefit for data scientists on the other hand is the ability to track the state of the numerous small components they produce and keep that information all in one place. It is extremely useful to be able to see which of the potentially thousands of scripts are dependent on an outdated or abandoned version of a language for example. Being able to quickly identify how ownership changes when staff changes is also very handy.

A Developer Portal provides many features, but in order to be useful to everyone, different user's needs and skills need to be considered. One way of resolving this could be limiting the advanced functionality for users who would perceive these functions as new complications to deal with. As such, it is essential to design such a portal contemporaneously whilst also considering the different types of users who will use this portal, highlighting the importance of co-creation.

Opportunities and future recommendations

Identification of the specific needs of specific groups of users is vitally important. The same service can provide benefits to diverse user groups though by framing the same information in different ways. Consulting these different user groups during the implementation process is also essential.